

Holmium Thin-Disk Laser at 2056 nm Based on Ho:KYW/KYW Epitaxy

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Outline

Introduction

Experimental

Liquid phase epitaxy

Thin-disk fabrication

Spectroscopy of Ho³⁺ ions

Ho:KYW thin-disk laser

Laser set-up

Output performance

Conclusions & Outlook

Motivation

Holmium (Ho³⁺) lasers:

- emission above 2 μm
(⁵I₇ → ⁵I₈)

- in-band pumping scheme

- remote sensing
- laser surgery
- materials processing
- pumping MIR OPOs

Thin-disk laser concept:

Appl. Phys. B 58, 365–372 (1994)
Scalable Concept for Diode-Pumped High-Power Solid-State Lasers

Appl. Phys. B 85, 549–552 (2006)

M. SCHELLHORN

Performance of a Ho:YAG thin-disc laser pumped by a diode-pumped 1.9 μm thulium laser

High Power Thin Disk Ho:YAG Laser

Jochen Speiser, Günther Renz, Adolf Giesen

Proc. of SPIE Vol. 7912 79120C-1

CW 2 at.% Ho:YAG thin-disk laser with **24 passes of pump** generated 9.4 W at ~2090 nm with a slope efficiency η of ~50%

Introduction

Monoclinic double tungstates

Substituted ions:

Y^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Lu^{3+}

Trivalent active ions:

Yb^{3+} , Tm^{3+} , Er^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Ho^{3+}

example: *KLuW* crystal

Optical indicatrix frame

Structural and thermal properties

High doping levels for the active ions

Moderate thermal conductivity

"Athermal" thermo-optic behaviour

Ln^{3+} spectroscopic properties

High transition cross-sections

Broad absorption and emission bands

Weak concentration-quenching

Strong Raman activity

Laser & Photon. Rev. 1, No.2, 179–212 (2007)

Introduction

2- μm MDT lasers

OPTICS LETTERS / Vol. 37, No. 3 / February 1, 2012
Efficient thin-disk Tm-laser operation based on Tm:KLu(WO₄)₂/KLu(WO₄)₂ epitaxies

OPTICS LETTERS / Vol. 40, No. 3 / February 1, 2015
In-band-pumped Ho:KLu(WO₄)₂ microchip laser with 84% slope efficiency

2010 / Vol. 18, No. 20 / OPTICS EXPRESS 20793
CW lasing of Ho in KLu(WO₄)₂ in-band pumped by a diode-pumped Tm:KLu(WO₄)₂ laser

LPE growth

The undoped KYW substrate was cut from a bulk crystal grown by the Top-Seeded Solution Growth (TSSG) method and oriented with the crystallographic **b**-axis normal to its face. It was 1 mm-thick.

The crack- and inclusion-free layer, a 3 at.% Ho:KYW ($N_{\text{Ho}} = 2.16 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), was grown by the liquid phase epitaxy (LPE) method using $\text{K}_2\text{W}_2\text{O}_7$ as a solvent.

Mutual orientation of the crystallographic (**a**, **b**, **c**) and the optical indicatrix axes (N_p , N_m , N_g)

Thin-disk fabrication

Cut and polished

AR/HR coated

Soldered to a
Cu heat-sink

Side view

Spectroscopy of Ho³⁺ ions

Spectroscopy of 3 at.% Ho:KYW/KYW epitaxy:

(a) **absorption**, σ_{abs} , and **stimulated-emission (SE) cross-section**, σ_{SE} , spectra, *black line* - luminescence spectrum;

(b) **gain cross-section**, $\sigma_{\text{SE}} = \beta\sigma_{\text{SE}} - (1 - \beta)\sigma_{\text{abs}}$, spectra for various inversion ratios $\beta = N_2(5I_7)/N_{\text{Ho}}$

(⁵I₇ ↔ ⁵I₈ transition of Ho³⁺ ions, light polarization $\mathbf{E} \parallel N_m$)

Laser set-up

CL and FL – collimating and focusing lenses, HR and AR – high-reflective and antireflection coatings, OC – output coupler.

The pump source was a Tm fiber laser (model IFL15, LISA laser products, OHG) emitting up to 12.5 W at 1960 nm (FWHM = 1.5 nm, unpolarized output with $M^2 \sim 1$).

Laser performance

Input-output dependences for the Ho:KYW thin-disk laser:
 (a) CW and (b) quasi-CW (duty cycle 1:2) operation modes;
 η - slope efficiency

Laser emission spectra

Typical laser emission spectra for the Ho:KYW thin-disk laser for various OCs (CW mode, 1-double-pass = single-bounce pumping, $P_{\text{abs}} = 1.52 \text{ W}$).

The emission spectrum of the Tm fiber laser is shown for comparison.

Double-bounce pumping

Comparison of the output performance of the Ho:KYW thin-disk laser in CW and quasi-CW operation modes for 1 and 2 double-passes (bounces) of pump: η is the slope efficiency, $T_{OC} = 3\%$.

Pump absorption:

1 bounce **14%**

2 bounces **25%**

Beam profile

3 at. % Ho:KYW thin-disk laser:
Spatial profiles measured at
different P_{abs} (CW mode, $T_{\text{OC}} =$
1.5%)

$$M_x^2 = 3.1$$

$$M_y^2 = 1.6$$

Spatial profiles of the output laser beam
measured at (a) low $P_{\text{abs}} = 0.39$ W and
(b) high $P_{\text{abs}} = 1.78$ W (CW, 1-double-
pass pump, $T_{\text{OC}} = 3\%$).

A and B – major and minor semiaxes of
the elliptic laser beam;
 X'_1 and X'_3 – principal axes of the
thermal expansion tensor of KYW.

Conclusions & Outlook

- CW Ho:KYW/KYW thin-disk laser generated 1.01 W at 2056-2059 nm with a slope efficiency η of 60% and a laser threshold of only 0.15 W (for a single bounce (double-pass) of pump at 1960 nm)
- Spectroscopy of Ho³⁺ ions indicates good suitability of Ho:KYW/KYW epitaxy for thin-disk lasers; while thermo-optic effects can be an issue

- Optimization of Ho³⁺ concentration (1-7 at.%); pump spot size and cavity geometry
- Passive Q-switching and mode-locking

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Thank you for your attention!

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